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VALIDATION OF MULTIPLEX PCR

The molecular characterization of *E. granulosus sensu lato* isolates is pivotal to understand the spatio-temporal epidemiology and infection evolution of *E. granulosus* species complex in many endemic areas. Also of paramount importance is the correct identification of cystic lesions caused by different cestodes (such as *E. multilocularis*, and closely related members of the genus *Taenia*) in the **intermediate hosts**, both in livestock and humans.

Boubaker and colleagues (2013) published a single-tube multiplex PCR allowing discrimination of *Echinococcus* at the level of species/genotypes. Moreover, Trachsel and colleagues (2007) developed a single-tube multiplex PCR targeting the **definitive host** for the identification of eggs belonging to *E. granulosus*, *E. multilocularis* and *Taenia* genus. This task is dedicated to the validation of these two molecular assays widely used for the detection of *Echinococcus* in definitive and intermediate hosts, targeting mitochondrial and nuclear markers.

This task focuses on the validation of molecular assays widely used for the detection of *Echinococcus* spp. in definitive and intermediate hosts, targeting mitochondrial and nuclear markers:

Assay 1: Boubaker et al. (PLoS Negl Trop Dis, 2013), a single-tube multiplex PCR allowing discrimination of *Echinococcus* at the level of species/genotypes.

Reference: Boubaker G, Macchiaroli N, Prada L, Cucher MA, Rosenzvit MC, Ziadinov I, Deplazes P, Saarma U, Babba H, Gottstein B, Spiliotis M. A multiplex PCR for the simultaneous detection and genotyping of the *Echinococcus granulosus* complex. PLoS Negl Trop Dis. 2013;7(1):e2017.

Assay 2: Trachsel et al. (Parasitology, 2007), a single-tube multiplex PCR targeting the definitive host for the identification of eggs belonging to *E. granulosus*, *E. multilocularis* and *Taenia* genus. Reference: Trachsel D, Deplazes P, Mathis A. Identification of taeniid eggs in the faeces from carnivores based on multiplex PCR using targets in mitochondrial DNA. Parasitology. 2007 Jun;134(Pt 6):911-20.

Assay 1. Validation process was developed as follows: first, a collection of reference parasitic material (worms, cysts and genomic DNA), provided by the [WHO Collaborating Centre for the Epidemiology, Detection and Control of Cystic and Alveolar Echinococcosis](#) (Rome, Italy), was selected for the experiments. The collection included at least two or more parasitic materials for each species of the Eg complex, for Em and for members of genus *Taenia* (*T. saginata*, *T. hydatigena* and *T. multiceps*). As validating requirements, results were considered valid when they resulted in an unequivocal species identification and were confirmed by three independent repeated experiments performed by two different technicians. Once experiment conditions were settled, the analytical sensitivity of the assay have been evaluated testing serial dilution of reference DNA. The assay was initially carried out with the original conditions described by the authors, resulting in the lack of six over 11 PCR targets needed for proper species identification. Thus, results were evaluated again under several modified conditions (i.e. using equimolar primer mix, running a gradient PCR to identify a better annealing temperature, testing different Taq polymerases, increasing reaction volumes and annealing time). Last, single primer pairs were tested independently to evaluate their performance and, when their working conditions were found proper, they were combined with other primer pairs to achieve a balanced amplification. In conclusion, lack of specific PCR bands or the appearance of aspecific PCR bands made impossible to execute the multiplex PCR and to get simultaneously all the targeted markers amplified, neither with the original conditions nor with the modifications tried. The high number of PCR markers targeted (n=11) by Assay 1 probably had a negative impact on the overall performance of this method.

Assay 2. The original paper describes a Multiplex PCR, which amplifies fragments of different sizes of DNA encoding portions of the mitochondrial genes (Subunit I of NADH dehydrogenase (ND1) for Em (PCR fragment 395 bp), and portions of ribosomal genes, subunit rrnS for Eg complex (117 bp), *Taenia* spp. (267 bp) and *Diphyllobotrium* spp. (267 bp). The original multiplex PCR was developed to identify eggs of the taeniid tapeworms from carnivores. In this validation process genomic DNA extracted from worms (Em and *Taenia* spp.) and cyst material (Eg) served as template for the multiplex PCR assay.

The validation process was developed as reported in assay 1. First, a collection of reference DNA, provided by the [WHO Collaborating Centre for the Epidemiology, Detection and Control of Cystic and Alveolar Echinococcosis](#) (Rome, Italy), was selected for the experiments. The collection included DNA for the species of Eg, Em and members of genus *Taenia* (*T. saginata*, *T. hydatigena* and *T. multiceps*, *T. polyacanta*, *T. hydatigena*, *Diphyllobotrium latum* and *Diphyllobotrium dendriticum*). As validating requirements, results were considered valid when they were specific (unequivocal species identification) and confirmed by three independent

repeated experiments performed by two different technicians. Once experiment conditions were settled, the analytical sensitivity of the assay has been evaluated testing serial dilution of reference DNA. The multiplex-PCR was initially carried out with the original conditions described by the authors. Gel electrophoresis resulted in the following results: Em amplicon showed the characteristic band of Taenia (267 bp), Taenia spp. amplicon always showed a non-specific band (around 200 bp), and the amplicon of Eg was often weak. Mixed infections were excluded by the nature of the matrices used, therefore the results were evaluated again under several modified conditions (i.e. using equimolar primer mix, running a gradient PCR to identify a better annealing temperature, testing different Taq polymerases, increasing reaction volumes and annealing time). After several tests, the concentration of the primers was changed to an equimolar primer mix (final concentration 0.2 μ M), which resulted in a correct identification of all species. Expanding the number of Em DNA tested (n=82) from different countries it was observed that 10 out of 82 samples showed the typical band of Em but also a light band typical of Eg (117 bp).

In conclusion, the single-tube multiplex PCR by Trachsel and colleagues (2007) has been proved to be a robust and reliable assay that can be used not only for the identification of taeniid eggs but extended to DNA extracted from different matrices. Nonetheless, problems with specificity of the PCR products can be eventually observed and the optimization of the primer concentration must be achieved. In this validation process an equimolar (0.2 μ M) primer mix showed the highest efficiency for the PCR reaction.